

Data Pitch

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Abstract

The purpose of the incubation services deliverable is to discuss the different services that are being set up for the six month accelerator programme. This document is the first deliverable on business services and is written before the start of the first accelerator programme. This deliverable will contain the original plan and ideas for the accelerator program. The plan will be revised at the end of the first programme and may be amended for the second round based on the feedback.

Executive summary

The purpose of the incubation services deliverable is to act as a guide to understand the services arranged for the startups and SMEs taking part in the Data Pitch accelerator. The acceleration programme will be tailored, for each start-ups and SMEs particular needs, potential and performance, with the objective of getting the best results out of each one, in a demanding and constantly challenging context. The acceleration programme will have a duration of six months and will focus on gaining and increasing business traction for its start-ups and SMEs while bringing innovation into well established companies.

Research and Tracking: At the start of the accelerator it is important to understand the stage that the companies are currently in and therefore the level of services and support that is needed to support them. The Data Pitch companies can be split into the following three stages: development stage, commercial stage and growth stage. Depending on the stages of the selected companies the accelerator services will be tailored to their needs. In order to ensure that the services that are being set up are relevant for the SMEs stages and knowledge level qualitative research on the participating companies will be conducted. This will mainly be done through Google forms but more information can be gained from the interviews and applications.

During the negotiation phase of the programme each company is tasked to prepare a work plan with a template provided by Data Pitch. The work plan sets out a 6 month plan containing details such as the full budget and how the Data Pitch grant will be used, the outputs of the full 6 month period, milestones and kpis that are expected and how the work will be undertaken. As an evaluation of the acceleration program, the consortium will conduct an experience survey to assess the performance of the program. The goal is to receive feedback from the start-ups and SMEs on the success of the programme.

Team Briefings: The first point of contact with the startups each week will be our Monday morning team briefings held every other week. These briefings are 45 minute Google Hangout sessions where the Data Pitch team shares the schedule for the coming week, general updates as well as upcoming opportunities.

Advisors: At the start of the accelerator programme each company will be allocated an advisor. The advisor is the company's first point of contact and the person who they will voice their concerns too. Each company will have at least one private monthly meeting with their advisor and more can be added on an ad hoc basis.

Mentors: The mentor network will consists of between 50-100 mentors from various industries. Mentors with different level of skills and expertise will be contacted and asked to join the mentor network. It is important to cover a wide basis of industries, knowledge and expertise to have the best support network available. Mentors can be previous startup founders, investors, corporate employees and other general experts. All mentors bios and skills will be listed in Mentornity, which is the mentorship tool which will be used throughout the programme.

Workshops: Workshops will be held every two weeks either in person or on Google Hangout. Workshops are organised around themes that either are relevant for all companies or around themes that have been identified through the initial research or through advisor meetings. Workshops can be internal or external.

Founder stories: Founder stories is a series of private monthly sessions with startups and a founder with an interesting story to share. Founder stories are intimate sessions where the companies will have a chance to listen and engage with founders who have had some success in their career and are willing to openly share their experience.

Networking: Networking is an integral part of building and growing a company. The purpose of networking will be to give the startups and SMEs the best possible exposure as well as to help them meet key stakeholders who can help them grow. Networking opportunities are also beneficial for Data Pitch in order to expand the community and the awareness of the programme.

Perks: Throughout the accelerator we will seek to offer the SMEs perks and discounts that will help them run their businesses more efficiently at lower costs. Perks will be added throughout the programme depending on the need and interest of the companies.

Grant: A grant of up to €100,000 in equity free funding will be given to each company based on their needs and the agreement made in their work plan.

Accelerator Events: For each six month virtual accelerator there will be three key events that are part of the accelerator curriculum that all companies are expected to attend in person. These are kick-off at the start of the programme, demonstration day around month four as well as demo day at the end.

Pr & Comms: PR and comms is an important aspect of creating a successful programme and raising the profile of Data Pitch. The PR team will be working throughout the accelerator period in order to provide various different opportunities for the startups and the SMEs.

Resources: In order to encourage further learning we are building a resource page on our website with informal education. When the accelerator starts the page can be accessed on www.datapitch.eu/resources

Community engagement: Various tools will be used to encourage community building and sharing within the accelerator. Each tool has a different purpose and this will be communicated to the startups at the start of the programme. These are email lists, Slack, Facebook groups as well as Whatsapp.

Schedule: The schedule for each accelerator programme will be slightly different depending on the availability of the workshop leaders and the scheduling of the in person events. Programme is generally scheduled for every other week so that every other week is a Data Pitch week and every other week is for implementation and progress.

This document is aimed to be used as a guide and as a living document. The business services proposed are designed to cover a wide range of situations and can be used as a template when tailoring an accelerator to specific companies needs. This document will also be revisited and revised as the first accelerator programme comes to a close and feedback has been provided.

Abbreviations and Definitions

AWS - Amazon Web Services hosting platform

B2B - Business to Business

B2C - Business to Consumer

CRM - Customer Relationship Management

EU - European Union

H2020 - Horizon 2020 European Research and Innovation programme

IPO - Initial Public Offering

MVP - Minimum Viable Product

ODI - Open Data Institute

ODINE - Open Data Incubator of Europe

PR - Public Relations

SME - Small and Medium Enterprise

SOTON - University of Southampton

Introduction

The purpose of the incubation services deliverable is to act as a guide to understand the services arranged for the startups and SMEs taking part in the Data Pitch accelerator. The portfolio of services offered to the selected start-ups and SMEs has been defined based on the experience of the ODI and Beta-i as well as previous accelerator programmes such as ODINE which was supported by two of the Data Pitch consortium partners ODI and SOTON.

The acceleration program will be tailored, for each start-ups and SMEs particular needs, potential and performance, with the objective of getting the best results out of each one, in a demanding and constantly challenging context. The acceleration program focuses on gaining and increasing business traction for its start-ups and SMEs while bringing innovation into well established companies and will have a duration of six months.

The business services are organized into the following groups:

1.1 RESEARCH AND TRACKING: How we selected the services and how we track the company's progress throughout the six month programme.

1.2 TEAM BRIEFINGS: Our first point of contact with the companies held every two weeks on Monday mornings. This is a quick update on the upcoming week.

1.3 ADVISORS: One to one or group meetings between the companies and their allocated advisor. The main purpose of these are to get an update on the progress and identify where help is needed.

1.4 MENTORS: The mentor network will be set up before the accelerator and the companies can access help on an ad hoc basis.

1.5 WORKSHOPS: Both small and large workshops will be organised to give startups and SMEs the skills and knowledge they need to grow their companies.

1.6 FOUNDER STORIES: These are more intimate monthly sessions between the companies and an invited guest who will be sharing their story.

1.7 NETWORKING: Networking opportunities will be organised throughout the programme. These will be both internal events with external invitees as well as external events.

1.8 PERKS: Perks will be organised on an ad hoc basis throughout the programme where a need has been identified.

1.9 GRANTS: The grants will be paid in installments as the company's progress and reach their milestones.

Apart from the specific services offered to startups and SMEs there will be other opportunities for them to grow their networks and scale their businesses. Data Pitch will arrange three in-person events which all companies are asked to participate in and these are the kick off, an internal demonstration day and a demo day. The startups will also be offered PR and Comms opportunities that can help them build traction.

In order to cover for gaps in knowledge and support companies that might need more help than others a resources web page will be set up allowing startups to continue their informal education on their own. Community engagement tools and a sample schedule of the accelerator can be found at the end of the deliverable.

1. Description of Services

1.1 *Research and Tracking*

1.1.1 Identifying the stage of startups and SME's

At the start of the accelerator period it is important to understand the stage that the companies are currently in and therefore the level of services and support that is needed to support them. The Data Pitch companies can be split into the following three stages:

Development stage - Pre-revenue startups

Companies at this stage are actively developing or starting to develop their products. These companies are not generating any revenue and are at a pre-commercial stage. These companies have yet to trial their MVP with clients and have not established product market fit.

Commercial stage - Finding product market fit

Companies at this stage have built at least an MVP or have a ready product and they are actively seeking users or clients to work with. The companies are testing their products commercially and are starting to generate revenue. They are actively finding out how to best sell and market their product.

Growth stage - Accelerating growth

Companies at this stage have found product market fit, they have paying customers and are ready to scale. They are focusing on identifying ways to streamline growth and how to run their company in the most efficient way.

Depending on the stages of the selected companies the accelerator services will be tailored to their needs. It is understood that all workshops and other services will not be relevant to all companies, however, companies are encouraged to engage with the accelerator and take advantage of the provided services as much as possible.

1.1.2 Surveys

In order to ensure that the services that are being set up are relevant for the SMEs stages and knowledge level qualitative research on the participating companies will be conducted. This will mainly be done through Google forms but more information can be gained from the interviews and applications. Some of the questions in the survey can be seen below:

- How big is your team?
- Has your company raised any funding? Please give details.
- Do you have any current customers? If so, who are they?
- How much revenue, if any do you have?
- What do you currently need help with?
- What are your biggest concerns?

- Have you ever presented your company in public?

This information will be used to help the programme set up as well as validate assumptions and prepare a schedule of services that will suit the participating companies.

1.1.3 Work Plan

During the negotiation phase of the programme each company is tasked to prepare a work plan with a template provided by Data Pitch. The work plan sets out a 6 month plan containing details such as the full budget and how the Data Pitch grant will be used, the outputs of the full 6 month period, milestones and kpis that are expected and how the work will be undertaken. The work plan will need to be completed and approved before the accelerator starts.

1.1.4 Milestone Reviews

To ensure that the Data Pitch consortium partners are properly updated on the start-ups and SMEs development, milestone reports will be required by the last day of M2, M4 and M6 during the six month acceleration program. The reports will be filled out via an online survey which the advisor will prepare and manage. A programme called AirTable which is a cloud collaboration service will then be used to record progress to ensure that all partners have an update on the status of the companies and their milestones. The company advisor will be working closely with the companies to ensure that they are progressing and will reach their upcoming milestones. The reviews is an occasion for everyone to see that enough progress has been made in order to reach the next stage of the programme. Milestone reports may include:

- Relevant kpis (users, financial, sales etc...)
- Tasks and activities that have been performed during the past two months.
- Tasks and activities scheduled for the next two months.
- Success stories as well as setbacks and difficulties experienced.
- Performance evaluation.

Time	Milestone
1st month, start	At the beginning of the programme the companies need to have fully completed their work plan and received approval from their Advisor. The first installment of the grant will be paid.
2nd month	After the second month the companies will need to prove that they have reached the milestone for month two set out in their proposal. This review will be virtual.
4th month	In month four of the programme there will be an in person milestone review taking place in Lisbon, Portugal. During this review the companies will need to demonstrate what they have built using the data provided. The companies that pass the month four milestone review will be able to take part in a demo day and will receive the 2nd installment of the grant.

6th month, final	The final milestone review will take place at the end of the accelerator period. In this review the companies will need to show their entire progress during the six month accelerator period. The companies who pass this review will be paid the third and last installment of the grant.
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1.1.5 Tracking

The progress of the selected SMEs will be tracked throughout the programme. This will be done mainly through regular contact with the advisor, through AirTable as well as through the milestone reviews.

1.1.6 Experience Survey

As an evaluation of the acceleration program, the consortium will conduct an experience survey to assess the performance of the program. The goal is to receive feedback from the start-ups and SMEs on the success of the program. The survey will be produced via Google Surveys and will include:

- Satisfaction with the program
- Areas of improvement
- Quality issues
- Any additional comments

The result of the experience survey will be used to receive feedback on the level of satisfaction as well as work on opportunities for improvement. The results will be shared internally with Data Pitch partners.

1.2 Team Briefings

The first point of contact with the startups each week will be our Monday morning team briefings held every other week. These briefings are 45 minute Google Hangout sessions where the Data Pitch team shares the schedule for the coming week, general updates as well as upcoming opportunities. During these sessions we ask the SMEs to share any wins they have had in the week and whether they have any blockers. Wins can be things such as securing investment, acquiring a new client, making a hire etc. These wins will be recorded by the comms team so that we can help with blog writing and publicity when possible. Blockers are things that are holding the company back from progressing on their work plan. The blockers are shared in order to identify whether another SME or the Data Pitch consortium can help the company to overcome their obstacles. Team briefings will be held on Google Hangout and all companies in the current cohort will participate.

1.3 Advisors

At the start of the accelerator programme each company will be allocated an advisor. The advisor

is the company's first point of contact and the person who they will voice their concerns too. Each company will have at least one private monthly meeting with their advisor and more can be added on an ad hoc basis. The purpose of these meetings is to discuss the progress of the company, where they need help each month and what Data Pitch can do to support them. When the advisor identifies that the company needs help to progress they will refer them to further support such as mentors who might have more expertise in the area. The role of the advisor is to listen, assess and direct the company towards the correct people and resources to ensure successful completion of the Data Pitch programme. The advisor will also identify where more information is needed from the data provider and will act as an intermediary in these discussions.

Every month the companies will also have a group session together with their advisor and all other teams who work with the allocated advisor. The groups will be made up of teams who are solving the same challenge, has a similar business model or similar needs for the duration of the accelerator. The purpose of the group advisor meetings is to share knowledge between the group. To address overarching challenges that identify solutions as a group. The purpose is also to encourage the group to work closer together and support each other.

1.4 Mentors

The Data Pitch mentor network is integral to the success of the programme. The mentor network will consist of between 50-100 mentors from various industries. The purpose of the mentor network is to outsource as much of knowledge and experience as possible in order to fully support the SMEs in their growth. Some mentors will commit to the programme prior to the start while others will join at a later stage. Some mentors will be asked to join during the programme if gaps in knowledge are identified. Mentors will be invited to be part of the Data Pitch community and can also opt to receive a free ODI membership if interested, however, they will not be paid for their time commitment.

1.4.1 Mentor expertise

Mentors with different level of skills and expertise will be contacted and asked to join the mentor network. It is important to cover a wide basis of industries, knowledge and expertise to have the best support network available. Mentors can be previous startup founders, investors, corporate employees and other general experts. Some of the skills that will need to be represented in the mentor network include:

- Marketing
- B2B sales
- B2C customer acquisition
- Fundraising
- Attracting press
- Data protection law
- Branding
- SaaS sales
- Agile development
- Presenting skills

1.4.2 Mentoring Process

All mentors bios and skills will be listed in Mentornity which is a mentorship tool which will be used throughout the programme. The mentors will be asked to provide an image, a bio as well as a list of key skills that they can help with. The database of mentors will be visible to all companies and can be filtered based on specific skills. Companies can then find and contact mentors on an ad hoc basis depending on their needs. Any interactions with mentors will be scheduled by the company and the mentors directly. Data Pitch will suggest mentors for companies but will not participate in the matchmaking process. All mentors will also be listed publicly on the Data Pitch website.

1.5 Workshops

Workshops will be held every two weeks either in person or on Google Hangout. Workshops are organised around themes that either are relevant for all companies or around themes that have been identified through the initial research or through advisor meetings. The purpose of the workshops is to offer educational opportunities to the SMEs and provide them with expert knowledge in important areas. Workshops can be internal or external. Workshops will be recorded and shared publicly on YouTube and will be saved on the Data Pitch channel as masterclasses.

1.5.1 Internal Workshops

There is a lot of knowledge within the consortium. The Open Data Institute (ODI) has a lot of experience with running startup programmes but also about data and how to build companies with data. The University of Southampton (SOTON) has a lot of knowledge on data, technology, law and European programmes. DAWEX bring extensive knowledge on data marketplaces while Beta-i has a lot of experience in startup accelerators and innovation programmes. Together the consortium cover many aspects of building and accelerating companies with data and internal workshops can be held on subjects such as building a business model, lean development, data protection law, GDPR as well as fundraising. When possible and when expertise is found within the consortium workshops will be run by internal members.

1.5.1 External Workshops

External key training professionals will be identified and invited to deliver workshops. These workshops will be in areas where startups and SMEs have identified a need and where it is possible to arrange a trainer within the time period of the accelerator. Some external workshop providers may be paid for their time when it is determined that the specific workshop is integral to the success of the programme.

Here are some sample themes for the workshops:

- Sales and Marketing
- Customer Acquisition
- Finding product/market fit
- Agile development
- Design

- How to sell to corporates
- GDPR and data protection
- Recruiting and retaining talent
- A/B Testing
- Fundraising techniques
- Angel/venture or corporate investment
- How to create a powerful pitch
- Presentation skills

1.6 Founder Stories

Founder stories is a series of private monthly sessions with startups and a company founder with an interesting story to share. Founder stories are intimate sessions where the companies will have a chance to listen and engage with founders who have had some success in their career and are willing to openly share their experience. Sample themes for uplifting founder stories sessions are selling your company, how to IPO or how to work with a really large corporate. These sessions may also be on difficult and sensitive subjects such as diversity within companies or on having to close down your company.

The Founder stories sessions are always held as intimate private sessions whether they are held in person or on Google Hangout. The sessions will never be recorded or shared. The purpose of these sessions is for the founders to get a deep intimate understanding of the highs and the lows of building companies and working in the technology industry. These sessions will also help founders understand how certain milestones such as acquisitions or mergers are implemented in practice.

1.7 Networking

Networking is an integral part of building and growing a company. Both the ODI and Beta-i have an extensive startup network which will be utilised in order to identify opportunities for the Data Pitch companies. The purpose of networking will be to give the startups and SMEs the best possible exposure as well as to help them meet key stakeholders who can help them grow. Networking opportunities are also beneficial for Data Pitch in order to expand the community and the awareness of the programme. Some of these opportunities will be internal events and some will be external opportunities for the SMEs to contribute to. There will be a shared calendar where new opportunities can be added by any accelerator partner. Opportunities will also be shared at the Monday morning briefings. SMEs are encouraged to participate in networking events especially when they are actively looking for clients or investment.

1.7.1 Data Pitch events

There will be three in person opportunities for the SMEs to come together and meet and these will be discussed in the 2.0 Accelerator Events section. At two of these events there will be a networking opportunity with invited stakeholders such as data providers, investors and mentors. The purpose of the first kick off meeting is for the SMEs to meet each other, the Data Pitch

consortium as well as some of our stakeholders. The purpose of the demo day will be to further widen their reach and community and introduce the SMEs to investors and clients that they can build valuable relationships with which can be valuable to them as they grow.

1.7.2 Peer to peer networking

Small peer to peer meetups will be organised with SMEs in the same cities, countries or regions. These will be organised on an ad hoc basis to foster further community knowledge sharing. The peer to peer meetups can be organised by a consortium partner, by an SME or by a mentor or another stakeholder. These events are very informal but can be valuable for peer to peer support and widening our networks.

1.7.3 External startup events

The Data Pitch consortium will have a list of upcoming events and networking opportunities which will be shared with the SMEs at the Monday briefings. The purpose of these events is to gain publicity for the SMEs, to gain beta testers and feedback, to find mentors, partners, recruits as well as investors. Some events will offer opportunities for the SMEs to pitch their company on stage and gain feedback from a panel of judges. These opportunities are very valuable in getting an outside perspective on their companies.

Here is a list of possible events for us to attend during the 2018 accelerator:

[Tech Chill](#), 8-9 February - Riga, Latvia

Opportunity to meet mentors, clients and investors from the region.

[InfoShare](#), 22-23 May - Gdansk, Poland

Opportunity to pitch, meet clients and investors.

[TheNextWeb](#), 24-25 May, Amsterdam, Netherlands

Opportunity to pitch, meet clients and investors.

[Pioneers Festival](#), 24-25 May - Austria, Vienna

Opportunity to pitch, meet clients and investors.

[The Europas](#), June, London, UK

Opportunity to have a booth, meet clients and investors.

[Unbound Festival](#), 18-19th July, London, UK

Opportunity to meet mentors, clients and investors.

1.8 Perks

Throughout the accelerator we will seek to offer the SMEs perks and discounts that will help them run their businesses more efficiently at lower costs. Perks will be added throughout the programme

depending on the need and interest of the companies. Offers will be shared with the companies in their welcome pack and will be added to the website on the resources page on an ongoing basis.

Examples of these perks are:

- AWS - Amazon Web Hosting credits of up to €10,000. These can be used to pay for hosting costs of the web solution.
- Google credits - Google offer credits for web hosting but they also have credits for other Google business services.
- Productivity tools, CRMs as well customer support tools such as Salesforce, Zendesk, Pipedrive, Intercom etc.

1.9 Grant

A grant of up to €100,000 in equity free funding will be given to each company based on their needs and the agreement made in their work plan. The grant can be used for specific costs that can be viewed in [Annex 2 in the Guides for applicants](#) on page 16.

The grant will be paid in three installments providing the SME can show enough progress at each milestone review to progress to the next stage. The installments are:

30% paid at the start of the accelerator at signing of the contract after the work plan has been approved

30% paid after the 4 month milestone review after the review has been approved

40% paid at the end of the programme providing the final milestone has been reached.

2. Accelerator events

Events play an integral part in building an engaged community around Data Pitch. For each six month virtual accelerator there will be three key events that are part of the accelerator curriculum that all companies are expected to attend in person. These are kick-off at the start of the programme, demonstration day around month four as well as demo day at the end.

2.1 Kick-off

Kick-off is a two day event held at the very start of the accelerator period. On the first day there will be an evening networking event with welcome drinks. This event will be held in London and will be attended by approximately 100 people. The purpose of the evening event is to welcome the companies in an informal setting, give them the chance to meet the Data Pitch consortium partners as well as each other and to get them excited about taking part in Data Pitch. During this evening event there will be some short speeches such as a welcome from the project co-ordinator, a few words from some of our data providers and a short 30 second elevator pitch from each participating company. Invitees to this event will be data providers, mentors, advisors as well as other key stakeholders such as investors.

The second day of the kick-off will be a full day event for the selected companies. At this event we will talk through the full schedule and setup of the virtual accelerator. The companies will have their first meeting with their advisors and they will be introduced to some perks and services that will be available to them throughout the programme. During this day we will also run our first in person workshop with the companies. The purpose of the second day is to give companies a clear understanding of the following six months and what is expected of them. This is also a chance to spend a bit more time with the companies in person which will make remote working easier going forward.

2.2 Milestone Review - Demonstration

The second internal in person event will be demonstration day which will be held in Lisbon, Portugal in month four of the virtual accelerator. This will be a one day event where companies will showcase their products and what they have built thus far. The demonstration day is an internal event for Data Pitch consortium partners and companies of the current cohort. No external stakeholders will be invited as the demonstration day will enable the companies to share their progress in a confidential setting. The demonstration day will be held around the time of the four month milestone review and companies who pass this milestone will be invited to take part in demo day.

2.3 Demo Day

Demo day will be held in London around month six of the programme. This event is an opportunity for companies who have reached a certain maturity to pitch their products publicly. The purpose of demo day is for the companies to secure press, new clients or investors for example and to have the opportunity to hone their storytelling and pitching skills. Demo day is an evening event which will be attended by an audience of 100-200 people. The audience will be made up of internal and

external stakeholders such as investors, mentors, corporate clients and data providers. At demo day each company will have 3 minutes to pitch their companies to the audience using a slide deck. They can angle the pitch however they like depending on their current needs. Data providers will also have an opportunity to come on stage to talk about their challenges and say a few words about the companies solving their challenge.

Sample demo day schedule:

17:30 Networking

18:00 Welcome toast from Data Pitch

18:30 Company pitches

19:45 Thank you

20:00 Networking

3. PR & Comms

PR and comms is an important aspect of creating a successful programme and raising the profile of Data Pitch. PR and comms will be used throughout the data innovation programme - publicising the accelerator and the companies taking part is an essential job for the communications team. The PR team will be working throughout the accelerator period in order to provide various opportunities for the startups and the SMEs. These include:

- Press announcement of the new startups and SME's and their business ideas
- Developing sector focused news stories around the challenges and the startups tackling them
- Creating engaging profiles of the startups on the Data Pitch website which we can refer media to
- Demonstrating the value of products created by the startups
- Honing in on any insights or research developed by the startups which could contribute to an engaging news story.

3.1 Company Updates

When companies first get selected to take part in Data Pitch they will be asked to complete a profile to give more information on their companies, their teams and their goals. This information will be used to draft blog posts on each company which will be publicised throughout the programme. Apart from the general blog posts companies will also be asked to provide regular updates to the comms team in order to identify any further press opportunities. These opportunities can range from a launch of a new product, news on closing an investment round or gaining a large client. The companies will also be encouraged to create blogs and vlogs throughout the programme and any material created around Data Pitch will be made public on social channels.

3.2. The Data Pitch newsletter

A Data Pitch newsletter will be created and sent out monthly with the main news from the accelerator, from the startups and SMEs and any upcoming events or opportunities. The newsletter will act as the best way for external interested stakeholders to keep up to date with the accelerator and be aware of upcoming deadlines such as the demo day and the opening of the new call.

3.3 Press opportunities

Press opportunities will be sought throughout the accelerator programme both on individual company news but also on Data Pitch as a whole. Some of the key opportunities to get press are at the launch of the programme and getting publications to write about the current cohort and the challenges that are being solved. The advantage of this is to start creating interest around the programme, give the companies some publicity and build up towards the launch of the second call. The second big opportunity is publicising demo day, achievements of the first cohort as well as the impact of the first accelerator programme. Demo day is a key opportunity as it will be at an important time for the companies as they are graduating and many will be looking for further investment and clients. The timing for demo day is also integral as the programme will be launching its second call around this time and any press and material being produced on it can be used in promoting the second call and encouraging more people to apply.

4. Resources

In order to encourage further learning we are building a resource page on our website with informal education. This page can be accessed on www.datapitch.eu/resources and will have resources such as:

- Online courses on starting a business
- Podcasts on building businesses
- Papers and journals on topics relevant to startups
- Webinar and videos on interesting topics
- Business books
- Newsletters
- How to guides
- Useful tech tools

5. Community Engagement

Various tools will be used to encourage community building and sharing within the accelerator. Each tool has a different purpose and this will be communicated to the startups at the start of the programme.

5.1 Email Lists

Email will act as the official form of communication throughout the accelerator. A google group with the whole cohort will be created and this will be used to send out official information such as deadlines, schedules, information on upcoming milestones and events. Email lists will mainly be used by the consortium partners but can also occasionally be used by the partners to share large updates or great opportunities.

5.2 Slack

A slack channel will be set up for day to day communication and an easy way to engage with the cohort. Slack will be used to share smaller daily updates, send reminders about upcoming events, discuss various subjects that the companies need help with and to share other interesting insights. Slack is a great way for companies to ask help from one another and create channels to discuss topics such as recruitment, B2B sales, website landing page optimisation etc.

5.3 Whatsapp

A whatsapp group will be created and the group will be used very rarely when there is a need to reach the cohort more urgently. The whatsapp group is particularly useful for in-person events or when everyone needs to be sent a reminder about an important event. This group is also useful when traveling and the startups need to be able to get hold of each other.

6. Schedule

The schedule for each accelerator programme will be slightly different depending on the availability of the workshop leaders and the scheduling of the in person events. The Data Pitch programme is generally scheduled on every other week so that every other week is a Data Pitch week and every other week is for implementation and progress. The purpose of this is to ensure that the companies are not too distracted by the accelerator programme and have time to focus on building their solutions.

6.1 Sample month:

Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4
IMPLEMENTATION			
	Team Briefing		Team Briefing
	Advisor Group Session		1-1 with Advisor
	Large workshop		Small workshop
			Founder Stories

6.2 Sample week 4:

TIME	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday
9:00					
10:00	Team Briefing				
11:00	Advisor 1-1				
12:00					
13:00					
14:00					
15:00			Small Workshop		
16:00					
17:00				Founder Stories	

6.3 Full accelerator schedule:

Month 1					
KICK-OFF					

Implementation	Month 2				
	Milestone Review	Month 3			
	Implementation	Implementation	Month 4		
			Milestone Review		
			Implementation	Month 5	
				Implementation	Month 6
					DEMO DAY
					Milestone Review

7. Conclusion

This document is aimed to be used as a guide and as a living document. The business services proposed are designed to cover a wide range of situations and can be used as a template when tailoring an accelerator to a specific company's needs.

This document will also be revisited and revised as the first accelerator programme comes to a close and feedback has been provided.

References

- [1] https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9IIZV_CjqLcOTVIYkh6V0xGNE0/view Guide for applicants call 2017 - Data Pitch website